

“ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF MARKETING OF MILK OF OMFED ALONGWITH CONSUMERS PERCEPTION AND BUYING BEHAVIOR TOWARDS IT IN CUTTACK DISTRICT OF ODISHA”

Swapnita Panigrahi¹, Dr. Sanjay Kumar² Madhusudan Tiwari³,

1. P.G. Student MBA (Agribusiness Management) Department of Agricultural Economics, Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India
swapnitasani98@gmail.com
2. Assistant Professor, Department of Agricultural Economics, Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India
sanjay.kumar@shiats.edu.in
3. **PhD. Research Scholar**, Department of Agricultural Economics, Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India
patrick6111997@gmail.com

(MS Received: 05.02.2023; MS Revised:06.03.2023; MS Accepted:07.03.2023)

MS 3026

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS,)

Abstract:

This paper presents an economic analysis of the marketing of milk produced by the Odisha State Cooperative Milk Producers' Federation (OMFED) in the Cuttack district of Odisha, India. The study aims to examine the consumer perception and buying behavior towards OMFED milk and analyze the economic factors influencing its marketing. The research was conducted through a survey of 120 farmers associated with OMFED in the Cuttack Sadar block of Cuttack district. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The study found that OMFED milk has a positive perception among consumers, and the majority of the households prefer to buy OMFED milk over other brands. The factors such as quality, relationship with dealer, price, availability, brand image and brand loyalty were found to be significant in influencing the consumer buying behavior towards OMFED milk. The study recommends OMFED to focus on maintaining the quality of milk, increase its availability, and offer competitive pricing to increase its market share.

Keywords: Economic analysis, Marketing, OMFED Milk, Consumer perception, buying behavior, Cuttack district, Odisha

Introduction:

India has the largest population of livestock in the world with 20% of the world's cattle and 50% of the world's buffaloes. One of the most successful development initiatives in India's post-independence era is the country's dairy sector. India, the world's top milk producer, boasts that it offers the most affordable and nutrient dense food. The market for milk and milk product is the largest and expanding market in the world. The dairy industry of India has been witnessing rapid growth. The handling of raw milk, milk processing, packaging and value added products are all possible investment opportunities in the dairy sector. The sole objective of the Indian dairy sector is to effectively utilize the country's resource in order to increase milk output and modernize milk processing.

Milk is one of the essential food items consumed by people worldwide. In India, milk is an integral part of the daily diet and is produced by various dairy cooperatives, including the Odisha State Cooperative Milk Producers' Federation (OMFED). OMFED was established in 1985 with the objective of developing the dairy industry in Odisha and providing a fair price to milk producers. OMFED procures milk from over 3 lakh dairy farmers and processes around 3.5 lakh liters of milk per day. The organization is engaged in the marketing of various milk products, including pasteurized milk, butter, ghee, paneer, and others.

The marketing of milk produced by OMFED in the Cuttack district of Odisha faces various economic challenges. The study aims to analyze the economic factors influencing the marketing of OMFED milk and examine the consumer perception and buying behavior towards it. The research is purely based on the objectives:

To study the socio-economic profile of the respondents in study area.
To identify different marketing channels involving marketing of milk and curd.

To evaluate marketing efficiency, market margin, marketing cost and price spread.

To study consumers perception and buying behavior towards this product.

To find out the problems in the marketing and processing faced by the concerned agency and suggest remedial measure.

Material and Method:

Selection of District: There are 30 districts and 3 divisions in Odisha. Out of which Cuttack district was selected on the basis of

maximum area under cattle rearing. The total area of Cuttack district is 3.932 km² as per land record of 2015-2016.

Selection of Sub-Division: There are 3 sub-divisions in Cuttack district namely Cuttack, Athagarh and Banki.

Out of which **Cuttack** was selected purposely.

Selection of Block: In Cuttack sub-division there are 14 blocks. Out of these **Cuttack Sadar** was selected purposively for the study. The climate and weather condition of the block is suitable for the cattle farming.

Selection of Villages: After obtaining a complete list of all the villages of Cuttack Sadar from the BDO office, 5% villages were selected randomly for the present study.

Selection of Respondents: From the selected villages, 10% farmers associated with OMFED were randomly selected from each category of each village on the basis of rearing capacity.

Tools and Techniques of Analysis:

Frequency-This measure was used to know the distribution pattern of respondent's variable wise and to categorize the problems perceived by respondents in order of importance.

Percentage-This measure was used for simple comparisons.

$$P = \frac{X}{N} * 100$$

Where,

P= Percentage

X= Frequency

N= Total number of respondents

1. Mean-The arithmetic mean is the sum of the scores divided by their number. This measure was used to categorize the dependent and independent variables.

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum Xi}{n} \quad i=1/N$$

Where,

X = Mean

Σxi = Sum of all the pairs in a distribution

N = Total number of items involved

Rank analysis - In a given dataset items are arranged into ranks on the basis of response of number of respondents to a particular option.

Likert scale- It is a type of survey scale which is used to measure variations like agreement, frequency, quality, likelihood etc. It contains a question that uses a 5 or 7-point scale to select.

Marketing efficiency- It is the degree of market performance.

Marketing efficiency = Output produced/Input used

Market margin- It is calculated by subtracting the net farm value equivalent of food sold at retail of the farm product from the retail price.

Market margin = Product price-Raw material Marketing cost- The total cost incurred on marketing by various intermediaries involved in the sale and purchase of the commodity till it reaches the ultimate consumer.

Marketing cost = Cf+Cm1+Cm2+Cm3+...+Cmn

Where,

C = Total cost of marketing

Cf = Cost produced by the producer farmer till the sale of the produce

Cmn = Cost incurred by the middlemen in the process of buying and selling

Price spread- It is the difference between the price paid by consumers and the net price received by the producer for an equivalent quantity of farm produce.

Price spread = consumer price-Net price of producer

Garrett ranking- To know the acceptance of respondents and constraints in marketing and processing of products, it has been used. It gives the change of orders of constraints and advantages into numerical scores.

Percent position = 100(Rij-0.5)/Nj

Where,

Rij = Rank given for ith factor by jth individual

Nj = Numbers of factors ranked by jth individual

Result and Discussion:

The result is a presentation of the findings of the given study.

Socio-Economic Status Of The Respondents:

Table 1: Gender of the respondents:

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	98	81.70%
Female	22	18.30%
Total	120	100%

Gender is one of the prime socio-demographic variables in this study. As gender affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction in their perception and socialization, men and females tend to have distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 120 respondents 98 respondents were male, that is 81.70% while the remaining 22 were female that is 18.30% of total sample.

Table 2: Age groups of the respondents:

Age(in years)	Frequency	Percentage
20-35(Young age group)	14	11.66%
36-50(Middle age group)	98	81.66%
Above 50 years(Old age group)	8	6.66%
Total	120	100%

From this Table it can be concluded that 14(11.66%) respondents are in the age group of 20-35 years, 98(81.66%) respondents are in the age group of 36-50 years, 8(6.66%) respondents are in age of above 50 years. Therefore, the majority of respondents are in the age group of 36-50 years that is the middle age group.

Table 3: On the basis of cattle no. of respondents:

Cattle no.	Frequency	Percentage
1-2(Small)	54	45%
3-5(Medium)	42	35%
More than 5(Large)	24	20%
Total	120	100%

Table 3. Reveals Farm size is one of the prime socio-demographic variables in this study. As farm size affects the buying decision, it has an essential association in market-related research. Due to the distinction in their perception and socialization, farm size tends to have distinct conclusions while buying. Out of the total, 120 respondents 54(45%) respondents were having small size farm, 42(35%) were having medium size farm and remaining 24(20%) were having large size farm.

Table 4: Caste of the respondents:

Category	Frequency	Percentage
General	40	33.30%
OBC	46	38.40%
SC/ST	34	28.30%
Total	120	100%

Table 4 reveals that 46 milk suppliers belonged to OBC category i.e. 38.40%, followed by 40(33.30%) of them belonged to general and only 34(28.30%) of them belonged to SC/ST.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents according to type of family:

Type of family	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Joint family	>4 members	98	81.70%
Nuclear family	<4 members	22	18.30%
Total		120	100%

Table 5 reported that majority of the respondents belonged to joint family i.e. 98(81.70%) and 22 members i.e. 18.30% belonged to nuclear family.

Marketing Efficiency, Market Margin, Marketing Cost And Price Spread In Existing Marketing Channel Of Milk:

Since, OMFED milk has only one marketing channel; there were no second marketing channels.

Channel: Farmer – Society – Milk Union – Federation (Procurement channel)

Table 6: Distribution of marketing cost, marketing efficiency, market margin and price spread in existing marketing channel:

S. No.	Particulars	Average value (Rs./ltr)
1	Cost incurred by the producer	
	Gross price	30.00
	Marketing price	30.00
	Net price	30.00
2	Cost incurred by the society	
	Purchase price from producer	30.00
	Value of wastage	1.00
	Sale price	34.00
	Profit	3.00
3	Costs incurred by the Milk Union	
	Purchase price from society	34.00
	Value of wastage	1.00
	Sale price	38.00
	Profit	3.00

4	Costs incurred by the Federation	
	Purchase price from milk union	38.00
	Value of wastage	0.65
	Sale price	40.00
	Profit	1.35
5	Sale price to consumers	40.00
6	Price spread	10.00
7	Marketing cost	2.65
8	Marketing margin	7.35
9	Marketing efficiency	4.00

From table 6, it was seen that the marketing price of the milk supplied by the farmer was Rs.30 and the net price received by him for 1 liter is Rs.30. Meanwhile the cost incurred by the society in purchasing the milk was Rs.30/liter, with Rs.1 as value of wastage and Rs.3 as profit per liter of milk. Finally the selling price of the milk from the society is Rs.34/liter with Rs.1 as value of wastage. Similarly, the milk union purchased the milk from the society at the cost of Rs.34/liter with Rs.1 as value of wastage and Rs.3 as profit per liter of milk. Thus, the selling price of the milk from the union to the

federation was Rs.38/liter. Simultaneously, the milk federation purchased the milk from the union as Rs.38/ liter, with Rs.0.65 as value of wastage and Rs.1.35 as profit, by which the final selling price of the milk was Rs.40/liter. Finally, the selling price of the milk to the consumers was Rs.40/liter. Eventually, the price spread was seen to be 10 rupees per liter, the marketing cost was Rs.2.65, the marketing margin was Rs.7.35, and the marketing efficiency was 4.00.

Consumers Perception And Buying Behavior Towards Milk:

Table 7: Consumers awareness about milk of OMFED:

Attributes	Frequency	Percentage
Have not heard about it	24	20%
Have heard about it but never used	45	37%
Seen products in neighbors home	09	08%
Used it	42	35%
Total	120	100%

Table 7 revealed that by interviewing and observation, out of 120 farmers 37% of surveyed population i.e. 45 members heard about the product but never used whereas 42 members (35%) have used it.

About 24 farmers (20%) have not heard about it. Apart from this there is still 8% of population i.e.9 farmers have seen products in peer house.

Table 8: Consumers perception and buying behavior:

Parameter	Frequency	Percentage
Quality	25	20%
Price	20	17%
Packaging	04	03%
Relation with Dealer	35	30%
Brand image	20	17%
Promotional Strategies	10	08%
Source of Information	6	05%
Total	120	100%

From table 8, it is founded that about 20% farmers(25) prefers to buy a product according to its quality, about 17% farmers(20) prefers the price of product, about 03% farmers(4) prefers the attractiveness of the packaging, 30% farmers(35) prefers OMFED products only because of the relationship with the distributor, 17% of the

farmers(20) buy milk product on the basis of Brand Image, about 8% farmers(10) buys milk products by convinced through promotional strategies, and 05% farmers(6) take information about products from their friends and neighbors or any other person.

Problems In The Marketing And Processing Faced By Concerned Agency And Suggest Remedial Measures:

Table 9: Constraints in the marketing of milk:

Particulars	Frequency	Ranking
Market is far from production point	30	II
High cost of transportation	35	I
Malpractices in weighing	27	III
Price fluctuation	18	IV
Illegal deductions	10	V

From table 9, it was revealed that high cost of transportation was ranked 1st with highest number of respondents response which is 35, followed by market is far from production point ranked 2nd with 30 respondents response, followed by malpractices in weighing ranked

3rd with 27 respondents response, followed by price fluctuation ranked 5th with 18 respondents response and lastly illegal deduction was ranked 6th with 10 respondents response.

Table 10: Suggestive measures to overcome constraints:

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Providing subsidies	45	37.5%
Regulating labor charges	30	25%
Providing quality inputs	20	16.66%
Providing credit in timely manner	10	8.33%
Maintaining standards	15	12.5%
Total	120	100%

From table 10, it was reported that most of the respondents suggested providing subsidies with 45 respondents suggestion which is 37.5%, followed by regulating labor charges with 30 respondents suggestion which is 25%, followed by providing quality inputs with 20 respondents suggestion that is 16.66%, followed by credit in timely manner with 10 respondents suggestion that is 8.33% and lastly maintaining standards with 15 respondents suggestion that is 12.5%.

Summary:

The study revealed that higher percentage of milk suppliers was having 1-2 cattle and small size farm (45%). Higher percentage of the milk suppliers were middle aged (81.66%), followed by young age (11.66%) and old age (6.66%). It can be seen that 81.70% of the milk suppliers were male and only 18.30% of the respondents were female. It is revealed that 38.40% of the milk suppliers belonged to OBC category, followed by 33.30% of them belonged to general category and only 28.30% of them belonged to SC/ST.

It was seen that the marketing price of the milk supplied by the farmer was Rs.30 and the net price received by him for 1 liter is Rs.30. Meanwhile, the cost incurred by the society in purchasing the milk was Rs.30/liter, with Rs.1 as value of wastage and Rs.3 as profit per liter of milk. Finally, the selling price of the milk from the society is Rs.34/liter. Similarly, the milk union purchased the milk from the society at the cost of Rs.34/liter with Rs.1 as value of wastage and Rs.3 as profit per liter of milk. Thus, the selling price of the milk from the union to the federation was Rs.38/liter. Simultaneously, the milk federation purchased the milk from the union as Rs.38/liter, with Rs.0.65 as value of wastage and Rs.1.35 as profit, by which the final selling price of the milk was Rs.40/liter. Finally, the selling price of the milk to the consumers was Rs.40/liter. Eventually, the price spread was seen to be 10 rupees per liter, the marketing cost was Rs.2.65, the marketing margin was Rs.7.35, and the marketing efficiency was 4.00.

It was revealed that Shelf life was the first constraint in marketing of

List of Tables:

Table No.	Content	Page No.
1	Distribution of milk supplier according to their gender	5
2	Distribution of milk suppliers based on their age	5
3	Distribution of milk suppliers based on their cattle no.	6
4	Distribution of milk suppliers according to their caste	6
5	Distribution of respondents according to their type of family	6
6	Estimation of marketing cost, marketing efficiency, market margin and price spread in existing marketing channel	7-8
7	Consumers awareness about OMFED milk	8
8	Consumers perception and buying behavior	9
9	Constraints in marketing of milk	9
10	Suggestive measures to overcome constraints	10

References:

1. Acharya, K. K., and Malhotra, R. (2020) Economic analysis of milk production in peri-urban dairy farms of Odisha, *Indian Journal of Dairy Science*, 73(2): 155-159.
2. **Agricultural Outlook. (2013-2022)** and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations.
3. Aneja, R.P. (2019) had conducted "A study on Dairying in

milk, followed by flavors, packaging, packing material and transportation cost were the 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th marketing constraints respectively.

It was reported that most of the respondents suggested providing subsidies with 45 respondents suggestion which is 37.5%, followed by regulating labor charges with 30 respondents suggestion which is 25%, followed by providing quality inputs with 20 respondents suggestion that is 16.66%, followed by credit in timely manner with 10 respondents suggestion that is 8.33% and lastly maintaining standards with 15 respondents suggestion that is 12.5%.

Conclusion:

The results show that the Socio economic status of the respondents found to be moderate with good economic background and great access to all the assets.

The study shows that there is immense scope to increase marketing of milk and manage it effectively so that the number of intermediaries is to be restricted and marketing costs and market margins to be reduced.

Acknowledgement

Words cannot express my gratitude to my professor Dr. Sanjay Kumar (Associate Professor, SHUATS) for his invaluable patience and feedback. I also could not have undertaken this journey without my mentor Mr. Madhusudan Tiwari sir (ph.D research scholar, SHUATS), who generously provided knowledge and expertise. Additionally, this endeavor would not have been possible without the generous support from the IJPAB (Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Biosciences) who financed my research.

I am also grateful to my classmates for their editing help, late-night feedback sessions and moral support.

Lastly, I would be remiss in not mentioning my family, especially my parents. Their belief in me has kept my spirits and motivation high during this process.

India". He analyzed the dairying and observed the factors contributed for its success and completed that it was a successful story. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Vol.75, No.1.

4. **Annual Report. (2019-20)** Department of Animal Husbandry, Dairying and Fisheries.
5. Ministry of Agriculture Government of India New Delhi,

www.nddh.org

6. **Bayan (2020)** studied the impact of becoming member of dairy co-operative society (DCS) on adoption of improved and production augmenting farm practices such as fodder cultivation. *Food and Agriculture Organization Animal and Health Paper*, 62: 23-24.
7. **Dash, S. et. al. (2020)**. Role Of dairy cooperative society in empowering women in rural Odisha. *International Journal of advanced science and technology*, 29(7): 461-467.
8. **D.S Jitendra Kumar (2020)** in their study "Impact of Dairy Co-operatives on Income and Employment in Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh - An Economic Analysis", came out with the findings that the income earned from dairying was more by members of societies than non-members. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, Volume 11, Issue 8.
9. **Jai Singh and Singh.V.K. (2015)** conducted a Study on "Price Spread and Marketing Margins in the Marketing of Milk in Hisar District of Haryana" and analyzed the present status of milk marketing in the State. *Indian Journal of Applied Research. Volume 3, Issue 4*.
10. **Nandal.R. S (2019)** analyzed the "Cost of Returns to a Farmer in Marketing of Buffalo Milk in Hisar District of Haryana". *Dairy Science Abstract*, 4472 (48): 526.
11. **Pandey. R.N (2018)**, made an attempt to analyses the "Production Costs and Utilization Pattern of Milk by Farmers in India". *International Conference, International Standard Book Number: 978-93-82702-25-2*.
12. **Pannu, R.S (2017)** conducted a study on the "Marketing Pattern, Cost and Margins of Milk in Hisar Districts of Haryana". *International Standard Book Number: 978-93-82702-25*.